

BLENDED DISTANCE LEARNING DELIVERY OF ARALING PANLIPUNAN AND THE STUDENTS COPING RESPONSES

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ABSTRACT

This study on Blended Distance learning Delivery and Student's Coping Responses aimed to determine the effectiveness of learning delivery system and teaching process between the student's coping responses as these factors affect the draw some implication on educational management. This study used descriptive correlation research design in conducting the study. A total of 217 came from 12 section among 513 Grade V students enrolled at Jose P. Rizal Elementary School Tayuman, St. Tondo Manila served as a respondent of this study. Data analysis was done using frequency counts, percentage, mean, and Pearson Product Moment Coefficient Correlation. The result of the study revealed that among the variables in learning delivery system only budget consumption for the internet connectivity had a positive significant relationship with the student's coping responses. It implied that budget consumption for the internet connectivity can affect when it comes performance of the students. Furthermore, findings illustrated a positive significant relationship between the quality of teaching and teaching strategies on the student's coping responses in terms of integration, domination, servility, and commitment. The study recommends the use of Blended Distance Learning Delivery in all disciplines to provide an easy way of teaching and learning and to develop the learning independence and self-proficiency of the learners.

Keywords: Blended Distance Learning Delivery, Student's Coping Responses, Learning Delivery System, Teaching Process.